

**NONLINEAR MODELS OF DEFORMATION OF LAMINATED
PLATES AND SHELLS MADE OF MULTI-COMPONENT MATERIAL**

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Annotation: The paper considers nonlinear models of laminated plates taking into account damage accumulation. The equations of equilibrium and boundary conditions are given on the basis of the variational principle and the calculation scheme using the method of successive approximations.

Keywords: three-layer plates and shells, models, equation of equilibrium, plasticity, viscoelasticity, forces and moments, damageability.

**KO‘P KOMPLEMENTLI MATERIALLARDAN KO‘PQATLAMLI
PLITALAR VA QOBIQLARNING DEFORMATSIYASINING
NOCHIZIQAVIY MODELLARI.**

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada ko‘pqatlamli plita va qobiqlarning chiziqsiz modellari yemirilishini hisobga olgan holda ko‘rib chiqilgan. Variation usul asosida harakat muvozanat tenglamasi va chegaraviy shartlari, hamda hisob sxemasi ketma-ket yaqinlashish ko‘rinishda keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: ko‘pqatlamli plita va qobiqlar, model, muvozanat tenglamasi, plastiklik, qovushqoq-elastik, zo‘riqish va momentlar, yemirilish.

When developing deformation models of layered plates and shell structures, polymeric materials and composites with different rheological properties are widely used along with traditional metallic materials. It is known that three-layer plates and shells composed of heterogeneous layers are the most widespread among the structural elements of inhomogeneous structure. Analysis of the calculation result and experiments show that under the influence of external loads in the material of the plate, panel can occur various types of damage, types of delamination and cracking [1-4]. These calculations can also be done using the ANSYS program [5-8].

A significant contribution to the development of the theory of layered, including three-layer elements was made by A.Ya.Aleksandrov, N.A.Alfutov, H.A.Akramov, V.V.Bolotin, E.I.Grigolyuk, Y.M.Grigorenko, V.I.Korolev, V.V.Moskvitin, G.A.Teeters, P.P.Chulkov, E.I.Starovoitov.

Following [9], we give the equations of state and boundary value problem for a three-layer plate made of polymeric materials taking into account damageability. For the bearing layers, which are considered viscoplastic, the Kirchhoff-Liave hypotheses are adopted. For viscoelastic filler ($h_3=2c$), the hypothesis of straightness of the normal and non-deformability in the z-axis direction is accepted.

Let us present the equations of state taking into account physical nonlinearity and damage accumulation for the plate layers [1]:

$$s_{\alpha\beta}^k = 2G_0^k \left[\vartheta_{\alpha\beta}^k (1 - \omega^k) - \int_0^t R^k(t-\tau') \varphi^k(\varepsilon_u^k) \vartheta_{\alpha\beta}^k(\tau) d\tau \right],$$

$$\sigma_{\alpha\alpha}^k = 3K_0^k (\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}^k - \alpha_0^k T_k), \quad \tau_\alpha = G_0^{(3)} \left[\psi_\alpha (1 - \omega^{(3)}) - \int_0^t R^{(3)}(t-\tau') \varphi^{(3)} \psi_\alpha(\tau) d\tau \right]. \quad (1)$$

where $R^k(t-\tau')$ - relaxation kernels of layer materials, $t'-\tau'$ -odified time, related to physical time $t-\tau$ and function by the relation $\eta(\chi_\alpha, t)$

$$t'-\tau' = \int_0^t \frac{d\xi}{a_\eta(\eta(\chi_\alpha, \xi))} \quad (2)$$

We take the following function as a characteristic of the damage accumulation degree:

$$\eta(x_\alpha, t) = (\omega + 1) \int_0^t (t' - \tau')^m \frac{d\tau}{t_0^{1+m} (\sigma_u(\tau, x_\alpha))} \quad (3)$$

According to the accepted hypotheses [2], we express the displacements and deformations in the layers through the displacements of the points of the median plane of the aggregate, and transverse shear :

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha z}^{(3)} = u_{\alpha, z}^{(3)} + w_{, \alpha} = \psi_\alpha \quad (4)$$

Hence after integration over z we obtain

$$u_\alpha^{(3)} = u_\alpha + z\psi_\alpha - zw_{, \alpha}$$

In the contact planes of the layers, the tangential displacements of the aggregate are as follows:

$$u_\alpha^{(1)} = u_\alpha + c\psi_\alpha - cw_{, \alpha}, \quad u_\alpha^{(2)} = u_\alpha - c\psi_\alpha + cw_{, \alpha}$$

Movements of points of external layers located at distance z from the coordinate surface:

$$\begin{aligned} u_\alpha^{(1)} &= u_\alpha + c\psi_\alpha - zw_{, \alpha} & c \leq z \leq c + h_1 \\ u_\alpha^{(2)} &= u_\alpha - c\psi_\alpha + zw_{, \alpha} & -c - h_2 \leq z \leq -c \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Internal forces and moments in the layers of the plate are determined by the formulas:

$$M_{\alpha\beta}^k = \int_{h_k} \sigma_{\alpha\beta}^k \xi_k dz, \quad T_{\alpha\beta}^k = \int_{h_k} \sigma_{\alpha\beta}^k dz, \quad Q_\alpha = \int_{h_3} \sigma_{\alpha 3}^{(3)} dz, \quad (6)$$

here the integrals are taken over the thickness of the corresponding layer h_k , and,

$$\xi_1 = z - c, \quad \xi_2 = z + c, \quad \xi_3 = z.$$

The equilibrium equations and boundary conditions are obtained using Lagrange's variational principle [5]

$$-\delta I + \delta A_1 + \delta A_2 = 0 \quad (7)$$

According to (7) we obtain equations of equilibrium and boundary conditions under loading of the three-layer plate:

$$T_{\alpha\beta, \beta} + P_\alpha = 0, \quad H_{\alpha\beta, \beta} - Q_\alpha = 0, \quad M_{\alpha\beta, i\alpha\beta} + q = 0 \quad (8)$$

Generalised forces and moments are introduced here

$$T_{\alpha\beta} = \sum_k T_{\alpha\beta}^k, \quad H_{\alpha\beta} = M_{\alpha\beta}^{(3)} + c(T_{\alpha\beta}^{(1)} - T_{\alpha\beta}^{(2)}), \quad M_{\alpha\beta} = \sum_k M_{\alpha\beta}^k + c(T_{\alpha\beta}^{(1)} - T_{\alpha\beta}^{(2)}) \quad (9)$$

Let us isolate the linear summand in equation (9). As a result, the equation of equilibrium has the form

$$\overset{0}{T}_{\alpha\beta,\beta} + p_\alpha + \bar{T}_{\alpha\beta,\beta} = 0, \quad \overset{0}{H}_{\alpha\beta,\beta} - Q_\alpha + \bar{H}_{\alpha\beta,\beta} = 0, \quad \overset{0}{M}_{\alpha\beta,\alpha\beta} + q + \bar{M}_{\alpha\beta,\alpha\beta} = 0. \quad (10)$$

Similarly, we transform the boundary conditions. All forces and moments included in the equations of equilibrium (10) are expressed through displacements w and shear. This calculation scheme is generalised for hollow shells [10-15].

Note that the method of successive approximations is used to solve boundary value problems. A zero solution is a decision in which the damageability function is not taken into account $\eta_k(x,t)$. If $\varphi=0$, then under the specified assumptions the boundary value problem of plasticity takes place. This problem is studied in a similar way under cyclic loading..

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